

An Open-Source CAMARA UE Location API Implementation over 3GPP NEF for AI-Native Crowd Assessment in 6G Networks

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Abstract—Network Exposure Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) are pivotal for 5G/6G ecosystems, enabling third-party developers to access granular network data via standardized interfaces. This paper presents a proof-of-concept (PoC) implementation that exposes 5G Core (5GC) User Equipment (UE) location data by integrating the Common API Marketplace and Repository Architecture (CAMARA) Device Location API, the Common API Framework (OpenCAPIF) framework and a 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)-compliant Network Exposure Function (NEF). We introduce a Transformation Function (TF) that bridges the gap between high-level CAMARA requests and 3GPP MonitoringEvent operations, simplifying developer interaction with complex core network functions. The framework is validated using an open-source 5GC environment through an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native crowd-mobility application. Results demonstrate the feasibility of standardized network exposure and provide design insights for future 6G exposure platforms.

Keywords—5GC (5G Core), Application Programming Interface (API), Common API Marketplace and Repository Architecture (CAMARA), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Open Common API Framework (OpenCAPIF), User Equipment (UE), Location

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution towards 5G and beyond (B5G) is driving a shift from vertically integrated communication systems to open, programmable platforms where network capabilities are exposed to external applications through standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). Application developers increasingly require access to contextual information such as User Equipment (UE) location, quality of service (QoS) and mobility events, in order to build network-aware services in the domains of smart cities, transportation and Industry 4.0 [1], [2]. However, the interface between developer-facing APIs and 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) network functions is still fragmented and existing solutions often rely on proprietary mechanisms or tightly coupled integrations that hinder portability and interoperability.

Recent initiatives such as Common API Marketplace and Repository Architecture (CAMARA) and the Common API Framework (CAPIF) aim to close this gap by providing harmonized northbound APIs and a common exposure framework for network capabilities, while the Network Exposure Function (NEF) defined by 3GPP offers standardized procedures to access 5G Core (5GC) services such as UE monitoring and location [3]. However, CAMARA and NEF operate at different lev-

els of abstraction. CAMARA exposes a simplified, developer-friendly interface, while the NEF uses 3GPP terminology, identifiers, and event types. As a result, a transformation layer is deemed necessary to perform a proper mapping that converts CAMARA API requests into valid NEF operations (e.g., monitoring event subscriptions) and then translates NEF responses back into the user-oriented format expected by the CAMARA interface [4].

In this context, there is a need for proof-of-concept (PoC) implementations that demonstrate how these architectural elements can be combined in practice and that provide open, reusable objects for the research and developer communities. This paper addresses this need by presenting an end-to-end (e2e) framework for UE location retrieval that integrates the CAMARA Device Location – Location Retrieval API with an OpenCAPIF-based exposure layer and a 3GPP-compliant NEF MonitoringEvent service in a 5GC deployment. The framework introduces a dedicated Transformation Function (TF) that decouples the CAMARA interface from the 3GPP data models and procedures, enabling transparent mapping between the two domains. Lastly, the above-mentioned framework is validated through an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native crowd assessment application demonstrating vertical utilization. Summarizing, the main contributions of the paper are:

- 1) The design of an architectural framework that connects an external application (vAPP) to 5GC UE location capabilities via CAMARA, OpenCAPIF and NEF using a well-defined invocation chain.
- 2) The specification and implementation of a TF that performs protocol and payload adaptation between CAMARA Device Location and 3GPP MonitoringEvent operations.
- 3) An open-source implementation and experimental evaluation of UE last-known-location retrieval, utilizing an AI-native crowd assessment application as vApp for demonstrating the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed framework.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Network Exposure Frameworks

The NEF was introduced in the 3GPP 5GC architecture to provide a secure, standardized entry point for accessing selected network capabilities and events from external applications. NEF exposes APIs for functions such as monitoring UE reachability, location and session information, enforcing policy, and mediating between external clients and internal

network functions. Through standardized procedures and data models, NEF aims to avoid ad hoc integrations and to ensure that exposure is governed by operator policies and subscriber consent [5]. To this end, UE location retrieval and monitoring are among the key capabilities that NEF can make available to third-party services, enabling location-based applications without granting direct access to core network internals.

CAMARA is an industry initiative that defines a portfolio of network APIs with a strong focus on developer experience, abstraction, simplification and cross-operator consistency. The Device Location – Location Retrieval API is one such interface, designed to allow application developers to query the last known location area of a device using a simple, Representational State Transfer (REST)ful schema that hides network-specific complexity [6]. CAPIF, on the other hand, is a framework specified to provide a common API exposure environment, including onboarding, discovery, authentication, authorization and routing of API invocations between API invokers and providers. OpenCAPIF is an open-source realization of this framework, offering a practical platform to implement and test CAPIF concepts in real deployments [7]. Together, CAMARA and OpenCAPIF provide an upper-layer abstraction through which application developers can access network capabilities exposed by NEF.

B. Current Research Works

A number of projects and demonstrations have addressed network exposure and 5GC integration, including prototypes that expose NEF capabilities to vertical applications, CAPIF-based gateways that unify access to heterogeneous network services, and early CAMARA implementations that showcase use cases such as quality-on-demand and device location. However, existing work is often limited in scope, focuses on specific platforms or non-public codebases, or does not provide a complete e2e chain from a CAMARA API, through a CAPIF-compliant exposure layer, down to a 3GPP NEF instance in a 5GC deployment. Furthermore, the details of protocol and payload translation between developer-friendly APIs and 3GPP interfaces are sometimes treated as implementation-specific, hindering reproducibility and reuse.

Existing work on Network-as-a-Service and CAMARA mainly focuses on presenting the general architectural framework, highlighting the separation between service APIs, network APIs, and a transformation function, and validating the concept with early QoS-oriented APIs such as Quality on Demand (QoD) in video-streaming scenarios [8], [9]. Other studies on 5G network exposure and NEF emphasize generic northbound APIs, monitoring and location primitives, or industrial Internet of Things (IoT) and vertical-focused demonstrations, but typically expose 3GPP capabilities directly and do not provide an intermediate CAMARA service layer or a reusable mapping pattern between CAMARA schemas and NEF MonitoringEvent payloads for mobility-centric applications [10], [11].

In contrast, the present work contributes an open, e2e realization of UE location exposure where a CAMARA Device Location API is integrated with a 3GPP-compliant NEF through an OpenCAPIF-based exposure environment and an explicitly documented transformation function. As a consequence, this research work addresses the gap of concrete, reproducible CAMARA–NEF integration for urban crowd assessment use cases.

III. CAMARA-BASED UE LOCATION API EXPOSURE FRAMEWORK

The proposed framework exposes 5GC UE location capabilities to external applications through a CAMARA Device Location API, while internally relying on a 3GPP-compliant NEF Location Reporting service integrated in the 5GC. The implementation follows an end-to-end invocation chain in which a vAPP issues a CAMARA Device Location – Location Retrieval request, which is processed by a CAMARA service, translated by a TF into a 3GPP Monitoring Event request. Consequently, this request is securely exposed through the OpenCAPIF framework to finally be served by a NEF instance connected to the 5GC after the request is authorized by the NEF instance under test. Figure 1 illustrates the Unified Modeling Language (UML) of the architectural flow mentioned above.

A. vAPP (API Consumer)

The vAPP represents an external Application Function (AF) that consumes network capabilities through developer-friendly APIs rather than direct 3GPP interfaces. In this framework, the vAPP issues Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) POST requests to the CAMARA Device Location – Location Retrieval API, providing device identifiers (e.g., phone number or IP address) and optional constraints such as maximum acceptable age of the location information, and receives a standardized location area description in the response. Authentication and authorization towards the CAMARA Framework are handled through OAuth 2.0 access token encoded as JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) Web Token (JWT), so the vAPP remains agnostic of operator-specific NEF integration details.

B. CAMARA Location Retrieval API

The CAMARA service exposes the Device Location – Location Retrieval endpoint as specified in the CAMARA API definition, acting as the main entry point for vAPPs. It validates incoming requests, enforces basic syntactic checks on identifiers and parameters, and encapsulates the business semantics of *retrieve last known device location* while hiding network-internal options such as Monitoring Event configurations or 3GPP network calls and logic for retrieving the requested location area information for the requested vAPP. Internally, the CAMARA service forwards requests to the TF component, and receives responses through it, providing the CAMARA Location data model to the vAPP. It comprises of a circle or polygon location information area of the specific cell that a device is registered, alongside with a timestamp of the location information event.

C. Transformation Function

The TF is a core element of the framework and acts as a mediation layer between the CAMARA data model and the 3GPP NEF Monitoring Event API. For UE location retrieval, the TF converts CAMARA Location Retrieval requests into 3GPP-compliant MonitoringEvent subscription, mapping CAMARA device identifiers to 3GPP UE identifiers, and configuring appropriate event types and reporting parameters for 3GPP location reporting feature and then performs the 3GPP request to 5GC. When NEF responses are received, the TF extracts the relevant location information (e.g., cell ID or location coordinates) and transforms it into the CAMARA Location schema, including last known location time and

Fig. 1. UML Sequence diagram for CAMARA UE Location Exposure Framework

area representation, while also translating error conditions into CAMARA-level error codes. This design decouples the CAMARA service and vAPP from 3GPP specifics, and allows reusing the TF logic for additional CAMARA–NEF mappings in future work.

D. OpenCAPIF Exposure Layer

OpenCAPIF provides the common exposure utilities for API invokers and providers, aligning with the 3GPP CAPIF specification. In the proposed framework, CAMARA acts as a CAPIF invoker towards NEF, while NEF acts as a CAPIF provider in the scope of CAPIF Framework. Both components are onboarded in OpenCAPIF, which handles API publishing, discovery, token issuance, request authentication, and authorization for the Monitoring Event API. NEF as a CAPIF provider application, onboarded and publishes its API into the CAPIF framework to obtain the required certificate to authenticate and authorize the incoming requests from the CAMARA service. On the other hand, CAMARA service as a CAPIF invoker application, onboarded into the CAPIF and then can discover the published APIs from the CAPIF framework to obtain a JWT token that associates with them. By utilizing that JWT token, CAMARA service can successfully communicate with the NEF under security constraints.

E. 5GC-enabled NEF

The NEF component is responsible for interfacing with the 5GC and executing the actual UE location operations. Upon receiving a Monitoring Event request for location reporting from CAMARA via OpenCAPIF, the NEF validates the subscription or request, interacts with the underlying 5GC functions like Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) to retrieve the UE’s most recent location, and formats the result according to the 3GPP Monitoring Event and Location data models. The implementation used in this work is an open-source NEF Monitoring Event service that exposes a RESTful API, parses

core network metadata to derive UE location and returns structured JSON responses that can be consumed by the TF and ultimately presented to the vAPP through the CAMARA Device Location API [12].

F. End-to-end (E2E) Interaction Flow

In the proposed framework, the interaction begins when the vAPP issues an HTTPS POST request to the CAMARA Device Location – Location Retrieval endpoint, providing a device identifier (e.g., phoneNumber). The CAMARA service validates the request, applies basic syntax checks, and forwards a representation to the TF, preserving the relevant identifiers and constraints while remaining agnostic to any 3GPP-specific details. The TF service then constructs a 3GPP-compliant Monitoring Event request towards the NEF, by mapping CAMARA fields to the corresponding UE identifiers and event configuration parameters required for location reporting and sending this request towards NEF under the scope of CAPIF framework for the exposure of common security mechanisms.

Regarding implementation as well as the sequence diagram as presented in Figure 1, the TF is part of the CAMARA service, while the CAMARA Location Retrieval API together with the TF is realized as a cloud native application. Upon receipt of a HTTP POST Request towards CAMARA API, the TF translates the CAMARA’s request payload to 3GPP-compliant NEF MonitoringEvent request body and then performs the 3GPP related request towards NEF for retrieving the last known location information. Once the NEF obtains the last known UE location information area from the 5GC response back to CAMARA service and particularly in the TF functional block. The response contains the 3GPP message from NEF, so the TF acts in reverse order and translate the 3GPP message into CAMARA-compliant response message. This means that the CAMARA Location schema model is constructed with regards to the 3GPP message that TF has been received, which is sent back to the vAPP containing the

Fig. 2. CAMARA-based UE Location exposure architecture

location information.

IV. LOCATION EXPOSURE VALIDATION

This section presents the validation of the proposed CAMARA-based UE location exposure framework through a use case targeting crowd-sourced activity detection. The implementation is built upon open-source components, including a 5GC, a Radio Access Network (RAN) emulator, a NEF implementation, an OpenCAPIF deployment and the CAMARA Location Retrieval service. All components are containerized and orchestrated within a unified experimental environment. Initially, the main functional modules are described in detail with regards to Figure 2. Subsequently, the targeted scenario is detailed, highlighting the framework’s applicability and performance in real-time location exposure events.

A. Evaluation Configuration

The complete testbed consists of the following elements:

- **5G Core (Open5GS):** A 3GPP-compliant 5GC implementation that provides the essential network functions, including AMF and other control-plane functions required for UE registration and mobility, enabling realistic signaling behaviour for location retrieval experiments [13].
- **RAN Emulator (UERANSIM):** An open-source RAN/UE emulator used to instantiate gNodeB (gNB) and UE instances, generate 5G Non-Access Stratum (NAS) signaling and attach UEs to the Open5GS deployment under different cell configurations [14].
- **NEF MonitoringEvent Service:** A RESTful NEF Monitoring Event API that adheres to 3GPP specifications and supports location reporting, enabling third-party applications to retrieve the current or last-known location of a UE while remaining independent from the underlying 5GC implementation [15], [16], [17].
- **OpenCAPIF Layer:** An OpenCAPIF deployment that acts as the common API Framework, onboarding the NEF as an API provider and the CAMARA service as an API invoker and exposing token issuance as well as authentication and authorization mechanisms. [18].
- **CAMARA Location Retrieval Service:** The CAMARA Device Location – Location Retrieval API implementation from the CamaraLocationRetrieval repository which handles developer-facing requests, maps them into NEF MonitoringEvent location re-

quests and translates NEF responses into CAMARA-compliant payloads.

- **vAPP Client:** vAPP utilizing REST client scripts and tools invoking the CAMARA Location Retrieval API, fetching the CAMARA Location data model and feeding the AI-Native crowd assessment app.
- **AI-Native Crowd Assessment App:** The AI-native application analyzes UE location data to assess crowd activity and detect abnormal conditions in urban environments. By identifying significant deviations in device density on a 5G cell, it enables real-time, data-driven monitoring for safety-oriented decisions.

All components run in isolated Docker containers and are interconnected via a dedicated virtual network, forming a fully reproducible, cloud-native 5G system. The experiment configuration (compose files, environment variables, and API definitions) is published in the CamaraLocationRetrieval and NEF repositories, enabling straightforward redeployment on different lab or cloud infrastructures [19], [20].

B. Operational Workflow

The validation workflow unfolds as follows. First, one or more UEs emulated by UERANSIM attach to the Open5GS core through a simulated gNB, causing the AMF and associated core functions to store UE context and location information (e.g., cell identifiers) according to standard registration procedures. Once the network state is established, the vAPP obtains a security token from OAuth2.0 service and issues an HTTPS POST request to the CAMARA Device Location – Location Retrieval endpoint. Upon receiving the request, the CAMARA service validates the input and forwards a request to the TF, which constructs a 3GPP-compliant Monitoring Event request for the NEF, mapping CAMARA parameters to UE identifiers and event configuration fields. This request is sent towards NEF, where it is validated against authentication and authorization with the usage of CAPIF’s server certificate that has been retrieved during the onboarding and publishing process of its service.

The NEF then interacts with the 5GC to retrieve the last-known UE location and returns a 3GPP compliant location payload, which the TF converts into a CAMARA Location Retrieval response before delivering it back to the vAPP. This e2e validation confirms that the CAMARA Device Location API can be used by external applications to obtain UE location information utilizing the standardized approach of CAMARA APIs as well as the encapsulated 3GPP native APIs, without directly coupling the vAPP to 3GPP-specific interfaces or data models. Figure 2 demonstrates the validation scheme, depicting all the components in and out of the 5G domain as well as, the vAPP exchanging messages with the rest of the services.

C. AI-Native Crowd Activity Assessment

To validate the framework’s practical utility, the AI-Native Crowd Activity Assessment is integrated as a specialized API Invoker within the OpenCAPIF ecosystem. This application functions as a proactive monitoring agent that consumes the standardized CAMARA Location Retrieval data model to detect abnormal crowd conditions through a closed-loop mechanism. Specifically, the framework considers data from a single 5G cell serving a public square where a network operator monitors activity levels for safety purposes. Such environments exhibit strong temporal variability driven by

daily routines or public events, which are reflected in the 5G network as fluctuations in the connected UE count. By utilizing the TF to bridge raw 5GC metadata with high-level logic, the AI component defines abnormal activity as a significant deviation from the expected UE count. Abnormally low activity may indicate disruptions, while abnormally high activity could signal unforeseen gatherings. This demonstrates a capability where standardized network exposure directly informs vertical-specific safety decisions using lightweight, data-driven machine learning (ML) models.

Due to the lack of publicly available datasets, a synthetic dataset has been constructed for controlled experimentation. The dataset consists of 30,000 samples, each representing a snapshot of a 5G cell serving the location of interest. Each sample includes two categorical variables, `time_of_day` (*morning, afternoon, night*) and `expected_activity` (*lower, normal, higher*), as well as a numerical feature `num_ues`, indicating the observed number of connected UEs. The target label `is_abnormal` indicates whether the observation corresponds to normal or abnormal activity. The contextual variables define the expected activity level of the cell under different conditions. An observation is labeled as abnormal when the UE count has a big deviation from the expected boundaries, capturing both unusually lower and unusually higher activity levels. To simulate a real-world monitoring scenario, the dataset intentionally includes noisy inputs and uncertainty.

Consequently, the problem is defined as a *binary classification task*, where the objective is to predict whether a given network snapshot corresponds to normal or abnormal activity using information exposed by the network. While the current evaluation utilizes a synthetic dataset to establish a functional baseline for this task, the architectural decoupling provided by OpenCAPIF and the TF ensures that the framework remains data-agnostic. This confirms that the proposed exposure path is ready for production-grade AI models consuming live RAN telemetry without requiring modifications to the underlying invocation chain or security handshake.

In the following sections, we describe the learning approach and evaluation methodology, and present results assessing the effectiveness of this integrated solution.

V. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

We evaluate the proposed abnormal activity detection task by comparing supervised ML models of increasing complexity. The objective is to assess whether simple linear approaches are sufficient, or whether more expressive models are required to capture the interaction between contextual information and observed UE counts under imperfect monitoring conditions.

Three classifiers are considered. Logistic Regression is used as a linear baseline, serving also as a sanity check. A Decision Tree classifier is included as a nonlinear baseline, capturing hierarchical decision rules over the input features. Finally, XGBoost is evaluated as the main model, leveraging gradient-boosted decision trees to model nonlinear interactions while remaining robust to noisy inputs. All models are trained using the same train/validation/test split. Performance is reported via several metrics analyzed below.

Table I summarizes the test-set performance of all evaluated models. Logistic Regression exhibits limited discriminative capability. The Decision Tree baseline achieves substantially higher performance, confirming the importance of

nonlinear, context-dependent decision rules. XGBoost consistently outperforms both baselines across all metrics, achieving the highest ROC-AUC, PR-AUC, and F1 score.

TABLE I. TEST-SET PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF EVALUATED MODELS.

Model	ROC-AUC	PR-AUC	F1
Logistic Regression	0.485	0.567	0.551
Decision Tree	0.971	0.944	0.884
XGBoost	0.984	0.973	0.906

Figure 3 and Figure 4 present the Receiver Operating Characteristic and Precision–Recall curves of the XGBoost classifier on the test set. The high area under both curves indicates strong separability between normal and abnormal activity across a wide range of thresholds.

Fig. 3. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve of the XGBoost classifier on the test set.

Fig. 4. Precision–Recall curve of the XGBoost classifier on the test set.

Overall, the results show that although simpler baseline models are valuable as reference points, they are not always capable of capturing the complex dependencies present in 5G network data. Gradient-boosted decision trees achieve superior performance, offering an effective balance between model expressivity and generalization. These findings support the use of lightweight machine-learning models for abnormal activity detection in network monitoring scenarios. This becomes especially important when models need to be deployed at the far edge of the network, where computational resources are often limited.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented an open-source PoC framework that exposes 5GC UE location capabilities to external smart mobility applications through a CAMARA Device Location API integrated with an OpenCAPIF exposure layer and a 3GPP-compliant NEF that exposes the MonitoringEvent API. By utilizing the CAMARA APIs, the framework decouples developer-facing APIs from 3GPP-specific data models and procedures, enabling a clean e2e invocation chain from vAPP to 5GC while preserving standards-based security and exposure semantics.

The implementation on a containerized testbed combining Open5GS, UERANSIM, OpenCAPIF, and the CamaraLocationRetrieval API demonstrates that UE last-known-location can be retrieved reliably via a fully standardized exposure path without requiring the application to interact directly with NEF or core-network internals. To this end, an AI-native crowd assessment utilized, fetching and analyzing UE location data to assess crowd activity and detect abnormal conditions in urban environments. Future work will focus on validating the existing framework with realistic data, assessing the results while supporting multi-domain deployments with different use cases. Furthermore, broader performance experiments on larger and more heterogeneous 5G/6G testbeds will be conducted to better understand scalability, latency, and robustness for smart mobility applications.

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